

Development of Progressive Failure Analysis Method for Composite Laminates Containing Openings with Digital Image Correlation

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ICCM22-I/446

Introduction

- Composite laminates are widely used in mechanical and aerospace industries.
- Composite laminate does not lead directly to fracture of the whole structure even if some plies are broken.
- The progressive behavior can be implemented more accurately through FEM, enabling more efficient design.

Contents

- Progressive failure analysis (PFA) method was developed based on crack band model implemented damage variables.
- Mechanical properties and fracture energies were obtained experimentally.
- Experimental results were compared with the computational results.
- Failure behavior of notched laminate was studied using the developed PFA model.

Material and properties

T700/Epoxy composite material properties

Property	Symbol	Units	Value
Longitudinal modulus	E_1	GPa	147.7
Transverse modulus	E_2	GPa	8.52
Shear modulus	G_{12}	GPa	4.59
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	-	0.3
Longitudinal tensile strength	X_T	MPa	2737
Transverse tensile strength	X_C	MPa	1600
Longitudinal compressive strength	Y_C	MPa	51.32
Transverse compressive strength	Y_C	MPa	201.08
Shear strength	S_{12}	MPa	81.0
Fiber tensile fracture energy	G_{fT}	kJ/m ²	180
Fiber compressive fracture energy	G_{fC}	kJ/m ²	100
Matrix tensile fracture energy	G_{mT}	kJ/m ²	0.30
Matrix compressive fracture energy	G_{mC}	kJ/m ²	1.71

Open hole tensile specimens

Type	Stacking sequence
TYPE 1	[0/+45/-45/90] _S
TYPE 2	[0/+45/0/-45] _S

- To compare with the results of proposed PFA model, open hole tensile tests were conducted.

Progressive failure analysis with crack band model

- PFA is performed to reduce the stiffness of composite materials based on the damage initiation criteria and evolution behavior.
- To reflect the reduction of the stiffness matrix, PFA uses damage variables.

$$\sigma = (1 - d)E\varepsilon,$$

Damage Initiation (Hashin failure criterion)

❖ Fiber tension failure mode: $f_{FT} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^2 + \tau_{13}^2}{S_A^2}\right) = 1$

❖ Fiber compression failure mode: $f_{FC} = -\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_C} = 1$

❖ Matrix tension failure mode: $f_{MT} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{S_T^2}\right) + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^2 - \tau_{13}^2}{S_A^2}\right) = 1$

❖ Matrix compression failure mode: $f_{MC} = \left[\frac{Y_C}{2S_T} - 1\right] \frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_C} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33}}{2S_T}\right)^2 + \frac{\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{S_T^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2 + \tau_{13}^2}{S_A^2} = 1$

Damage evolution (Crack band model implemented damage model)

Crack band model

$$d = \frac{2G_c}{\sigma_0 L_c} \rightarrow \delta_{f,eq}^f = \frac{2G_c^f}{\sigma_{f,eq}^f}$$

Damage variable

$$d_I = \frac{\delta_{f,eq}^f(\delta_{f,eq} - \delta_{f,eq}^f)}{\delta_{f,eq}(\delta_{f,eq} - \delta_{f,eq}^f)}$$

At each failure mode

$$d_f = \begin{cases} d_{fT} & \text{if } \delta_{11} \geq 0 \\ d_{fC} & \text{if } \delta_{11} < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$d_m = \begin{cases} d_{mT} & \text{if } (\delta_{22} + \delta_{33}) \geq 0 \\ d_{mC} & \text{if } (\delta_{22} + \delta_{33}) < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$d_s = 1 - (1 - d_{fT})(1 - d_{fC})(1 - d_{mT})(1 - d_{mC})$$

Test Procedures

Open hole tensile test

- Test machine : MTS 810 hydraulic test machine
- Test rate : 1 mm/min, Sampling rate : 100 Hz

Digital image correlation (DIC)

- Strain field was obtained using DIC equipment

Results and conclusions

1) Mesh dependency

- Crack-band-model applied PFA shows less influence of mesh dependency. (8.5% error of the maximum load)
- The elements of this model are fractured considering the fracture energies in each failure mode.

2) Load-displacement curve comparison

- The maximum load difference between the experiment and PFA results was only 2.3% and 0.59% for type-1 and type-2 specimens.

3) Strain comparison

PFA strain contour

DIC strain field

Strain gauge vs. PFA vs. DIC

- The maximum value observed from the PFA result was 0.01873, and that from the DIC result was 0.01804.

4) Progressive behavior of open hole composite laminate

5) Conclusions

- Progressive failure analysis method was developed using Hashin failure criterion and crack band model.
- PFA results were compared with experimental results
- The analysis results were in good agreement with the experimental ones (L-D curve, strength, strain field trend, and strain values)
- The suggested model, which allows for a good representation of behavior of notched geometry and less mesh dependence, is expected to benefit in the designing process of complex composite structures.